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Abstract: A great number of available pharmaceuticals are chiral compounds. Although they are usually manufactured as racemic mixtures, they can be enantioselectively biodegraded as a result of microbial processes. In this paper, a biodegradability assay in similar conditions to those recommended in OCDE tests of enantiomers of trimeprazine (a phenothiazine employed as a racemate) is carried out. Experiments were performed in batch mode using a minimal salts medium inoculated with an activated sludge (collected from a Valencian Waste Water Treatment Plant, WWTP) and supplemented with the racemate. The concentration of the enantiomers of trimeprazine were monitored by means of a chiral HPLC method using a cellulose-based chiral stationary phase and 0.5 M NaClO₄/acetonitrile (60:40, v/v) mobile phases. Experiments were performed at three concentration levels of the racemate. In parallel, the optical density at 600 nm (OD₆₀₀) was measured to control the biomass growth and to connect it with enantioselectivity. The calculated enantiomeric fractions (EF) offer the first evidence of enantioselective biodegradation of trimeprazine. A simplified Monod equation was used as a curve fitting approach for concentration (S), biodegradation (BD), and for the first time, EF experimental data in order to expand the usefulness of the results. Precision studies on S (repeatability conditions) and, for the first time, EF (intermediate precision conditions) were also performed.

Highlights

First evidence of enantioselective biodegradation of trimeprazine.

Optical density at 600 nm, to control the biomass growth, connected with enantioselectivity.

Enantiomeric fraction-time profiles modelled for the first time.

Enantiomeric fraction precision performed for the first time under intermediate precision conditions.

1 Trimeprazine is enantioselectively degraded by an activated sludge in ready
2 biodegradability test conditions

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11 **ABSTRACT**

12 A great number of available pharmaceuticals are chiral compounds. Although they are
13 usually manufactured as racemic mixtures, they can be enantioselectively biodegraded
14 as a result of microbial processes. In this paper, a biodegradability assay in similar
15 conditions to those recommended in OCDE tests of enantiomers of trimeprazine (a
16 phenothiazine employed as a racemate) is carried out. Experiments were performed in
17 batch mode using a minimal salts medium inoculated with an activated sludge
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22 performed at three concentration levels of the racemate. In parallel, the optical density
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24 enantioselectivity. The calculated enantiomeric fractions (EF) offer the first evidence of

25 enantioselective biodegradation of trimeprazine. A simplified Monod equation was used
26 as a curve fitting approach for concentration (S), biodegradation (BD), and for the first
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30 **Keywords:**

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34 Trimeprazine

35 Curve fitting

36 Precision

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41

42 **1. Introduction**

43 Among emerging pollutants, drugs are probably the main concern of regulatory
44 authorities due to their huge consume. Drugs, their metabolites and their degradation
45 products could reach the environment mainly due to poor removal rates in Waste Water
46 Treatment Plants (WWTP), and by improper disposal of unused medicines (Kümmerer,
47 2009). The presence of these compounds in the environment has been extensively
48 reported (Petrie et al., 2015; Geissen et al., 2015; Ebele et al., 2017; Sanganyado et al,
49 2017). However, although the great efforts made by regulatory authorities and scientific
50 community, not much is known about the impact of this kind of compounds on the
51 environment and human health (Wong, 2006; Stanley et al., 2006; Stanley et al., 2007;
52 Kasprzyk-Hordern, 2010; Ribeiro et al., 2012).

53 A great number of currently available drugs are chiral compounds and many of
54 these are marketed as racemates. Enantiomers have different interactions with
55 physiological chiral molecules leading to different biological responses that affect living
56 organisms in different ways. The enantioselectivity in ecotoxicity and biodegradation
57 processes is evident and comparable to the events in medical/biomedical fields
58 (Kasprzyk-Hordern, 2010; Ribeiro et al., 2014a).

59 The biodegradability, defined as the capacity of a molecule to be degraded by
60 microorganisms forming more simple final products, is an essential parameter to know
61 the risk that involves the dispersion of a compound into the environment. This property
62 depends on the chemical structure of the compound as well as on the physicochemical
63 conditions under which the degradation process takes place. Biodegradability assays are
64 designed to test a chemical substance as the sole carbon source in a mixed inoculum
65 (Thouand, 2014). The OECD tests for ready biodegradability have been devised as
66 screening methods to determine whether a chemical is potentially easily biodegradable,

67 which contribute to gain knowledge in the field of water and environmental research.
68 There are evidences of enantioselective biodegradation of chiral compounds in the
69 environment. The quantification of the enantiomeric fractions (EF) during the
70 biodegradation process is of key importance to evaluate the health and environmental
71 risk. However, there is not much research done on this subject.

72 Some studies have been focused on the EF evaluation directly in wastewaters.
73 They involve drugs of abuse and pharmaceuticals (Vázquez-Roig et al., 2014;
74 Kasprzyk-Hordem and Baker, 2012), amphetamines (Evans et al., 2016) and seven
75 selected chiral pharmaceuticals in WWTP influents and effluents (Ribeiro et al., 2014b).
76 Other approaches have been based on *in vitro* biodegradability assays. They simulate
77 the degradation processes of chemicals in soils, surface waters or in activated sludge,
78 generally in the presence of oxygen (Kowalczyk et al., 2015). The subsequent
79 separation and determination of the individual enantiomers of the original compound (or
80 its metabolites) in the test solution by analytical techniques, mainly liquid
81 chromatography, allow the estimation of EF. Using this laboratory scale methodology,
82 enantioselective evaluation of biodegradation for fluoxetine and norfluoxetine (Ribeiro
83 et al., 2014b; Moreira et al., 2014), amphetamine based compounds (Evans et al., 2016,
84 Bagnall et al., 2013), atenolol, metoprolol and fluoxetine (Ribeiro et al., 2013a),
85 alprenolol and propranolol (Ribeiro et al., 2013b) and venlafaxine (Li et al., 2013) have
86 been reported. Recently, S. Evans et al. reported an enantioselective biodegradation
87 study involving chiral pharmaceuticals (amphetamines, beta-blockers and
88 antidepressants) (Evans et al., 2017).

89 Trimeprazine or alimemazine is a tricyclic antihistamine, similar in structure to
90 the phenothiazine antipsychotics, but differing in the ring-substitution and chain
91 characteristics. trimeprazine is not used clinically as an anti-psychotic. It is used

92 principally as an anti-emetic, to prevent motion sickness, or as an anti-histamine in
93 combination with other medications in cough and cold preparations. trimeprazine is
94 largely used as antipruritic agent, but also for insomnia and oral premedication in
95 paediatric day surgery (Drug Information Portal, 2017).

96 In this paper, the enantioselective biodegradation of trimeprazine enantiomers is
97 studied by means of a biodegradability assay in similar conditions to those
98 recommended in OCDE tests. For this purpose, experiments at three concentration
99 levels of racemic trimeprazine are performed in batch conditions using an activated
100 sludge inoculum from a local WWTP. A RPLC method for chiral separation of
101 trimeprazine enantiomers is developed. In the literature, some references about the
102 chiral separation of enantiomers of trimeprazine using electrophoretic (Liu et al., 2005;
103 Martinez-Gomez et al., 2007) and liquid chromatographic methods using chiral
104 stationary phases (Van Overbeke et al., 1995; Oguni et al., 1995; Sanchez et al., 2012)
105 have been reported. Complete separations of enantiomers of trimeprazine have been
106 obtained using a α_1 -glycoprotein (AGP) column and hydroorganic mobile phases
107 containing 20 mM phosphate buffer pH 3.5:2-propanol 99:1 (v/v) (Sanchez et al.,
108 2012); a cellulose tris(3,5-dimethylphenylcarbamate) (Chiralcel OD-R) stationary phase
109 and mobile phases containing 0.1M sodium hexafluorophosphate: acetonitrile 60:40
110 (v/v) (Oguni et al., 1995) and a cellulose tris (4-methylbenzoate) (Chiralcel OJ-R)
111 stationary phase and mobile phases containing 1M sodium chlorate: acetonitrile:
112 methanol 40:15:45 (v/v) (Van Overbeke et al., 1995).

113 To the best of our knowledge, neither biodegradation nor enantioselective
114 biodegradation for trimeprazine has been reported in the literature. Thus, one aim of this
115 work is to provide the first evidence of enantioselective biodegradation of this emergent
116 contaminant. Additional objectives are: (i) to connect the enantioselective

117 biodegradation with the microbial growth; (ii) to apply a curve fitting approach for
118 concentration, biodegradation, and also for the first time, enantiomeric fraction data
119 over time in order to expand the usefulness of the results; (iii) to perform a precision
120 study on S and EF data and, for the first time, under intermediate precision conditions.

121

122 **2. Material and methods**

123 *2.1. Instrumentation*

124 An Agilent Technologies 1100 chromatograph (Palo Alto, CA, USA) with a
125 quaternary pump, a UV–visible variable wavelength detector, a column thermostat and
126 an autosampler was used. Data acquisition and processing were performed by means of
127 the Chemstation software (A.09.03 [1417], ©Agilent Technologies 1990-2002). For the
128 determination of the enantiomers of trimeprazine, several polysaccharide-based chiral
129 stationary phases were tested: Chiralart Cellulose-SC (cellulose tris (3,5-
130 dichlorophenylcarbamate); 3 μm , 150 \times 4.6 mm i.d.; YMC Separation Technology Co.,
131 Ltd., Tokyo, Japan); Lux Cellulose-1 (cellulose tris(3,5-dimethylphenylcarbamate); 3
132 μm , 150 \times 4.6 mm i.d.; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA); Lux Cellulose-3 (cellulose
133 tris(4-methylbenzoate); 3 μm , 150 \times 4.6 mm i.d.; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA)
134 and Lux Amylose-2 (amylose tris(5-chloro-2-methylphenylcarbamate); 3 μm , 150 \times 2.0
135 mm i.d.; Phenomenex). The mobile phases flow rate was 1.0 mL min⁻¹ in all cases
136 except when using the Lux Amylose-2. In this last column the mobile phases flow rate
137 was 0.4 mL min⁻¹. The injection volume was 2 μL , the detection was performed in the
138 UV at 254 nm. The columns were thermostatted at 25 °C.

139 For samples mixtures preparation, 15 mL conical sterile polypropylene tubes
140 (Deltalab, S.L., Barcelona, Spain) were used. Disposable sterile filter pipette tips (Capp
141 Expell, Odense, Denmark) were also used. For the biodegradability assays, a shaking

142 incubator with temperature control (WiseCube® Wis-30, Witeg Labortechnik GmbH,
143 Wetheim, Germany) was used. Prior to the measurement of the microbial growth,
144 incubated samples were subjected to agitation in a vortex mixer (Velp Scientific Vortex,
145 Usmate, Italy). Microbial growth was monitored by measuring the optical density (OD)
146 of the cultures at 600 nm with an Epoch 2 microplate reader (Biotek Instruments Inc.,
147 Vermont, USA) and 96-well plates with UV transparent flat bottom (Corning,
148 Kennebunk, ME, USA). Samples were stored at -80 °C in an ultra-low temperature
149 freezer (U570 Premium, New Brunswick Scientific, Herts, UK) until chromatographic
150 analysis.

151 Prior to injection into the chromatographic system, samples were centrifuged
152 (Hettich Lab Technology, EBA 20, Tuttlingen, Germany) and filtered through
153 disposable 0.22 µm polyethersulphone syringe filters (Frisenette, Knebel, Denmark).
154 Mobile phase solutions were vacuum-filtered through 0.22 µm Nylon membranes
155 (Micron Separations, Westboro, MA, USA) and were degassed in an Elmasonic S60
156 ultrasonic bath (Elma, Singen, Germany) prior to use. A Crison MicropH 2000 pHmeter
157 (Crison Instruments, Barcelona, Spain) was employed to adjust the pH of the buffer
158 solutions.

159

160 *2.2. Chemicals and solutions*

161 All reagents were of analytical grade. Ammonium acetate, hydrochloric acid (37
162 %), sodium hydroxide, sodium perchlorate monohydrate, acetonitrile and methanol
163 (®Multisolvent, HPLC grade) were from Scharlau, S.L. (Barcelona, Spain).
164 Ammonium formate, diethylamine and potassium hexafluorophosphate were from
165 Acros Organics (Geel, Belgium).

166 Ultra Clear TWF UV deionized water (SG Water, Barsbüttel, Germany) was
167 used to prepare solutions. Different solutions were tested for the preparation of the
168 mobile phases. Ammonium acetate buffer (10 mM, pH 8.0) was prepared in the same
169 way from ammonium acetate. 100 mM hexafluorophosphate and 500 mM perchlorate
170 solutions were prepared by dissolving in water the appropriate amount of potassium
171 hexafluorophosphate and sodium perchlorate monohydrate, respectively. The mobile
172 phases were prepared by mixing aqueous or buffer solutions with the tested organic
173 modifier to obtain the working concentration.

174 The minimal salts medium (MSM) solution used in the biodegradability assays
175 was prepared with the following composition per liter (Ribeiro et al., 2013a,b): 2.1 g
176 Na_2HPO_4 (Panreac Química, S.A., Barcelona, Spain); 1.4 g KH_2PO_4 (Panreac); 0.2 g
177 $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Scharlau Chemie S.A., Barcelona, Spain); 0.5 g $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (Scharlau),
178 and 10 mL of a trace elements solution with the following composition per liter: 2.0 g
179 NaOH (Scharlau); 12.0 g $\text{Na}_2\text{EDTA}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Scharlau); 1.4 g $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Panreac);
180 1.3 g $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Panreac); 10 g Na_2SO_4 (Panreac); 0.7 g $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck,
181 Darmstadt, Germany); 0.3 g $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Panreac); 0.1 g $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck); 0.1 g
182 $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck); 0.5 mL H_2SO_4 (98 %) (Scharlau).

183 The activated sludge sample was kindly donated by General de Análisis
184 Materiales y Servicios, S.L (GAMASER, S.L., Valencia, Spain), a laboratory and
185 inspection entity of the Group “Aguas de Valencia”. They were obtained from the
186 aerated tanks of a municipal WWTP (Quart Benàger, Valencia, Spain), which receives
187 domestic, agricultural, livestock and industrial wastewater from eight Valencian towns
188 with a surface area of 164171 ha and a population of approximately 1 million. Its
189 average flow rate is 30318 m^3/day . The plant operates on activated
190 sludge/nitrification/phosphorous removal process (where phosphate is biologically

191 removed), with a hydraulic retention time of 24 h. The activated sludge sample was
192 collected in plastic flasks and stored at 4 °C until usage.

193 Trimeprazine hemi(+)-tartrate was from Sigma (St. Louis, MO, USA). Stock
194 standard solutions of 1000 mg L⁻¹ of *rac*-trimeprazine was prepared by dissolving the
195 adequate amount of the compound in methanol. To prepare the calibration standards, an
196 intermediate stock solution of 100 mg L⁻¹ of *rac*-trimeprazine was prepared by dilution
197 of the corresponding 1000 mg L⁻¹ stock solution in the MSM. Calibration solutions of
198 approximately 2, 5, 10, 20 and 30 mg L⁻¹ were prepared by dilution of the intermediate
199 stock solution of 100 mg L⁻¹ in the MSM. For the biodegradability assays, working
200 solutions of approximately 5, 10 and 20 mg L⁻¹ of *rac*-trimeprazine were prepared by
201 dilution of the 1000 mg L⁻¹ stock solution in the MSM. The solutions were stored under
202 refrigeration at 5 °C.

203

204 2.3. HPLC method

205 The enantiomers of trimeprazine were separated using the Lux Cellulose-1
206 column. The optimized mobile phase was 500 mM sodium perchlorate/acetonitrile
207 (60:40, v/v). In both cases, the separation temperature was set at 25 °C and the mobile
208 phase flow rate was 1.0 mL min⁻¹.

209

210 2.4. Biodegradability assays

211 The biodegradability assays for the enantiomers of trimeprazine were performed
212 in batch mode at three concentration levels (4.8, 9 and 18 mg L⁻¹ of *rac*-trimeprazine in
213 the incubation tubes). For the preparation of the samples mixtures, 15 mL uncovered
214 sterile tubes were used. Samples mixtures containing 3000 µL of the corresponding
215 working solution of *rac*-trimeprazine inoculated with 100 µL of the activated sludge

216 (total sample volume of 3100 μL) were prepared. Independent samples were prepared
217 for each concentration level and each incubation time studied. All experiments were
218 done in duplicate, using tubes of a volume five-fold superior to guarantee the aeration of
219 the cultures. The samples were incubated on a shaking incubator (150 rpm) at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$
220 under natural light cycles. At ten prefixed incubation times (0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 10, 14, 18
221 and 23 days), two test tubes of each concentration level were taken, and when necessary
222 to compensate solvent evaporation ultrapure water was added to get a total volume of
223 3100 μL . Then, mixtures were vortex mixed for 20 s and an aliquot of 200 μL of each
224 tube was taken to measure the OD of the cultures at 600 nm. After OD measurement,
225 samples were frozen at -80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ until HPLC analysis (described in section 2.3). Abiotic
226 degradation of the enantiomers of trimeprazine was evaluated using 100 μL of ultrapure
227 water instead of the activated sludge inoculum, under the same conditions as samples.
228 Prior to HPLC analysis, the samples were centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 15 min and the
229 supernatant was filtered. Experimental conditions used (i.e., trimeprazine concentration
230 and volume of inoculum) were chosen according to OECD guidelines (OECD, 1992).

231

232 *2.5.-Precision studies*

233 Precision statistics considering repeatability and intermediate precision
234 conditions (including the factor time) were used according to an approach described
235 elsewhere (Bonet-Domingo et al. 2006, Maroto et al., 1999). Duplicated results
236 obtained from biotic assays were organized in a matrix $X_{N_r \times N_s}$, where N_r are the number
237 of replicates ($N_r = 2$) and N_s are the number of series or ‘runs’ (in this case, incubation
238 times). The approach analyses the $X_{N_r \times N_s}$ data matrix by means of analysis of variance
239 (ANOVA). From the residual mean square (MS_r) and the between-run mean square
240 (MS_{run}), the repeatability standard deviation (s_r), between-run standard deviation (s_{run})

241 and standard deviation of the run mean or grand mean (s_{mean}), can be calculated using
242 the following equations (Eqs. (1) to (3)):

$$s_r^2 = MS_r \quad (1)$$

$$s_{run}^2 = \frac{(MS_{run} - MS_r)}{Nr} \quad (2)$$

$$s_{mean}^2 = \frac{MS_{run}}{Nr} \quad (3)$$

243

244 2.6. Biodegradation kinetics

245 Common biodegradation models proposed in the literature (the nonlinear Monod
246 equation and its simplified version, the Michaelis-Menten-like equation) are unreliable
247 approaches in terms of kinetic parameters accuracy. This is due to the linear parameter
248 correlation (Robinson and Tiedje, 1983; Liu and Zachara, 2001). This is particularly
249 evident for imprecise data, low substrate concentration (S) and few incubation times (t).
250 Despite this, both Monod and Michaelis-Menten-like equations often provide good fit
251 between the model (S vs. t fitted curve) and the experimental data (S vs. t experimental
252 data; discrete points), even with wrong estimates. The aim in this work is not to estimate
253 kinetic parameters (that anyway could be unreliable), but to be able to model the
254 substrate concentration vs. time (S vs. t) experimental data in order to approach
255 biodegradation vs. time (BD vs. t) or the enantiomeric fraction vs. time (EF vs. t) fitted
256 curves. The Michaelis-Menten-like equation does not account to the biomass
257 concentration and the microbial yield coefficient, necessary for the Monod equation.
258 Thus, this equation was used as a simplified Monod model in this work (Eq. (4)).

$$\frac{dS}{dt} \sim \left(-\frac{V_m S}{K_s + S} \right) \quad (4)$$

259 Where V_m approaches is the maximum specific growth rate and K_s approaches the half
 260 saturation constant for growth. In the simplified approach, V_m is assumed constant
 261 (strictly speaking it depends on the biomass concentration, which in general varies with
 262 t). An explicit solution for Eq. (4) can be written (Goudar and Strevett, 2001), based on
 263 the Lambert W function (S as a function of the time, t ; $S = W\{t\}$; (Corless et al., 1993)):

$$S = K_s \cdot W \left\{ \frac{S_0}{K_s} e^{\left(\frac{S_0 - V_m \cdot t}{K_s} \right)} \right\} + \text{offset} \quad (5)$$

264 Where S_0 is the initial concentration of the compound. Eq. (5) could provide estimations
 265 of V_m and K_s by nonlinear parameter estimation. If degradation profiles do not reach
 266 zero, an offset term can be considered for fitting the function to the experimental data
 267 (Her et al., 2015).

268

269 2.7. Software and data processing

270 For curve fitting purposes, the NLINFIT.m function in MATLAB® R2016b
 271 (MathWorks, Natick, Massachusetts) has been used. It estimates the coefficients of a
 272 nonlinear regression function using iterative least squares estimation. Algorithmic
 273 details of the explicit Lambert W function (Eq. (5)) can be found in (Her et al., 2015).

274

275 3. Results and Discussion

276 3.1. Chiral chromatographic analysis

277 For the separation of enantiomers of trimeprazine, different polysaccharides
278 stationary phases Chiralart Cellulose-SC, Lux Cellulose-1, Lux Cellulose-3 and Lux
279 Amylose-2 were assayed (see experimental section). Using an ammonium acetate pH
280 8/acetonitrile (40:60) + 0.1% diethylamine mobile phase, only partial resolution of
281 trimeprazine enantiomers were obtained using/with Chiralart Cellulose-SC and Lux
282 Cellulose-1 stationary phases (R_s values of 0.5 and 0.3, respectively). Using these
283 columns, different chaotropic agents, like potassium hexafluorophosphate and sodium
284 perchlorate solutions, were assayed. The use of 100 mM potassium
285 hexafluorophosphate and acetonitrile 60:40 (v:v) mobile phases did not provide the
286 separation of trimeprazine enantiomers in spite of the results reported by Oguni and
287 coworkers using a stationary phase similar to Lux Cellulose-1 (Oguni et al. 1995).
288 Adequate resolution value ($R_s = 2.2$) and retention times (13.6 and 14.8 min for the first
289 (E1) and the second (E2) eluted enantiomers, respectively) for the enantiomers of
290 trimeprazine were obtained using a Lux Cellulose-1 column as stationary phase and a
291 500 mM sodium perchlorate/acetonitrile (60:40, v/v) mobile phase (See Figure 1).

292 Using these experimental conditions, a concentration value of 1 mg L^{-1} of
293 racemic trimeprazine (0.5 mg L^{-1} of each enantiomer) was considered the limit of
294 quantification. Peak areas below this concentration level were too low for quantification
295 purposes. The calibration curves of each enantiomer were obtained by injection of
296 standard solutions containing racemic trimeprazine in the $1\text{-}30 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ range (5
297 concentration levels) (see section 2.2). Table 1 shows the calibration statistics obtained
298 for each enantiomer. As can be observed, for both enantiomers, satisfactory results were
299 obtained ($R^2 > 0.99$).

300

301 *3.2. Enantioselective biodegradation results*

302 The biodegradability assays for the enantiomers of trimeprazine were performed
303 in batch mode by duplicate at three concentration levels (section 2.2). Sample tubes
304 containing trimeprazine and inoculum in MSM medium were collected and analysed at
305 different times (0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 10, 14, 18 and 23 days). Similarly, samples tubes
306 containing trimeprazine in MSM medium (abiotic assays) were analysed at the same
307 times. According to OECD (OECD, 1992), benzoic acid was used as reference
308 substance to ensure that the microbial community in the test system is active. A
309 complete biodegradation of benzoic acid (20 mg L^{-1}) was achieved in less than 48 h in
310 the experimental conditions used, indicating the adequacy of the inoculum and thus, the
311 validity of the trimeprazine assays.

312 Figure 1 shows two chromatograms corresponding to $t = 0$ and 18 days. As can
313 be observed, the peak areas of the first (E1) and second (E2) eluting enantiomers of
314 trimeprazine are lower in the second case. This fact indicates that a degradation process
315 has occurred. Moreover, in the second chromatogram the peak area of E1 seems lower
316 than those of E2. This suggests that an enantioselective biodegradation process has
317 occurred.

318 Figure 2 shows the concentration profiles (S vs. t experimental data; two
319 replicates) of enantiomers at initial trimeprazine racemate concentration of 9 mg.L^{-1} (i.e.
320 $S_0 = 4.5 \text{ mg.L}^{-1}$). As can be seen, a similar concentration decay is observed during the
321 first days for E1 and E2 enantiomers until day ~ 4 . However, different profiles for the
322 enantiomers are evident during the following days until the end of the experiment. This
323 behaviour could be attributed to a shift in the microbial communities during the
324 biodegradation of trimeprazine. Biodegradation in communities of diverse
325 microorganisms is a complex process (combination of different effects, kinetics),
326 especially when enantiomers are present (competition, enantiomerization, etc.) where

327 several degradation pathways could sequentially operate, some being enantioselective
328 and others not. Similar behaviour has been previously described for other compounds
329 and it was attributed to time-dependent changes in the composition of the microbial
330 community (Evans et al., 2017).

331 Anyway, the enantioselective biodegradation mechanism is confirmed in Fig. 2.
332 The results also indicate that the concentration profiles are stabilized at higher times; so,
333 no further degradation is expected. Similar results (not shown) were obtained for the
334 other concentration trimeprazine racemate concentrations assayed.

335 On the other hand, abiotic assays indicate relatively low degradation in absence
336 of inoculum (< 20%) for the concentration levels studied. These results indicates that
337 abiotic elimination of the compound can be considered non-significant [ISO 9888:1999]
338 and the degradation estimated in biotic assays can be considered as biodegradation.

339 In order to control to the biomass growth, the optical density (OD, at 600 nm;
340 OD₆₀₀) profile was obtained. The OD₆₀₀ can be considered proportional to the biomass
341 growth (Shuler and Kargi, 2002). The OD₆₀₀ values (in the range 0-1) were
342 superimposed in Fig. 2, just for comparison purposes. Individual phases of the typical
343 batch growth curve (Shuler and Kargi, 2002) can be perceived, bearing in mind the
344 experimental design used. After an initial lag growth phase (~2 days), a short
345 exponential phase (~2 days) is observed, to continue with a stationary/decline phase.
346 The last phase could explain the stabilization in the concentration profiles. Similar
347 results were obtained with the other trimeprazine racemate concentrations. Interestingly,
348 when comparing both the concentration with OD₆₀₀ profiles, it can be deduced that the
349 stage of enantioselective biodegradation mainly coincides with the last growth phase,
350 more than with the exponential phase.

351 To obtain the enantiomeric fraction profiles of trimeprazine enantiomers the
352 enantiomeric fraction (EF) was calculated for each incubation time according to
353 (Bagnall et al., 2012):

$$EF = \frac{S_{E1}}{S_{E1} + S_{E2}} \quad (6)$$

354 Where S_{E1} and S_{E2} refers to the estimated concentration of enantiomers at a
355 given incubation time (e.g. S values in Fig. 2). Figure 3 shows the mean EF values
356 together with their standard deviation ($EF \pm s$) for each time during the biodegradation
357 process. The horizontal line at $EF = 0.5$ represents no enantioselectivity. Consistently
358 with conclusions of Fig. 2, until day ~4, EF values close to 0.5 are obtained (differences
359 could be attributed to the method imprecision). Only during the last growth phase, EF
360 values below 0.5 are observed and they are stabilized around 0.4-0.45.

361 The results in Fig. 3 correspond to the intermediate concentration level (9 mg.L^{-1})
362 ¹⁾ evaluated in this work. Comparable EF patterns were observed for the other two
363 trimeprazine concentration levels studied. In fact, the grand mean of the EF values,
364 considering the five last incubation times (where EF is almost constant), were $0.44 \pm$
365 0.03 , 0.43 ± 0.04 and 0.43 ± 0.05 , for the low, intermediate and high trimeprazine
366 concentration levels studied, respectively (The error terms correspond to s_{mean} ; Eq. (3)).
367 This represents a clear evidence on a moderate enantioselectivity in the biodegradation
368 process of trimeprazine, with this activated sludge, with a minimum EF (i.e. maximum
369 enantioselectivity) around 0.44, independent of S_0 . Further verification with sludges
370 from other plants would be necessary to confirm if the results could be generalized.

371

372 *3.3. Kinetic assessment of the data. Curve fitting.*

373 In this work, the model kinetic parameters (the maximum specific growth rate,
374 V_m , and the half saturation constant for growth, K_s) estimated from Eq. (5) were not
375 taken into account, since they cannot be considered accurate due to their linear
376 correlation. Moreover, errors can increase depending on the S_0/K_s ratio (Liu and
377 Zachara, 2001); and K_s is *a priori* unknown. In addition, when the degradation profiles
378 do not reach zero (as in this work), an offset term in Eq. (5) has been proposed to model
379 the entire profile (Her et al., 2015). It is important to realize that this fact should alter
380 the estimated parameters. Moreover, it is possible that the experiment is conducted
381 while the sludge is in an adaptation phase to the current conditions, which could
382 difficult the mathematical treatment of the data. Finally, it is impossible to guarantee a
383 unique kinetic behaviour during the entire process since communities of diverse
384 microorganisms exist, as stated before. A deeper study on this matter is beyond the
385 scope of this study.

386 The S vs. t experimental data were adjusted to Eq. (5) (including the offset term)
387 just with the purpose to obtain S vs. t fitted curves that fit well the experimental data (a
388 suitable objective as stated in section 2.6). Figure 2 shows the fitted models (S vs. t
389 fitted curves; solid lines). From the S vs. t fitted curves of two enantiomers derived
390 using Eq. (5), an enantiomeric fraction versus time (EF vs. t) fitted curve can be
391 obtained (considering Eq. (6)). The EF vs. t fitted curve is included in Fig. 3. Despite
392 the noticeable uncertainty of the EF data, the fitted curve shows a reasonable agreement
393 with the EF points. The curves at the three concentration levels were similar.

394 EF vs. t fitted curves provide a simple manner to estimate EF at different times
395 or vice versa. For instance, the EF vs. t fitted curves confirm the minimum EF value at
396 0.44 (at the maximum t value). To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that
397 an EF vs. t fitted curve to the experimental data has been reported. Similarly, from the S

398 vs. t fitted curves, curves for the percentage of biodegradation can also be estimated
399 (considering the expression $BD = 100 (S_0 - S) / S_0$). Figure 5 shows the biodegradation
400 versus time (BD vs. t) fitted curves obtained for each enantiomer at the three
401 concentration levels evaluated (for clarity experimental values are not included). The
402 time where the BD = 50 % line cross a biodegradation versus time fitted curve is an
403 estimate of $t_{1/2}$. BD vs. t fitted curves provide a simple manner to estimate $t_{1/2}$ values
404 (independently from the parameters), as well as the BD estimates at different times or
405 vice versa.

406 According to these plots, at the highest concentration level (curves 5 and 6), both
407 enantiomers have similar half-life (~4.5 days), being still negligible the
408 enantioselectivity of the biodegradation. For the intermediate concentration level
409 (curves 3 and 4), $t_{1/2}$ differs between E1 and E2 (~4.5 and ~6 days, respectively), with
410 an incipient enantioselective biodegradation. The most extreme situation occurs at the
411 lowest concentration level (curves 1 and 2). While E1 has $t_{1/2}$ ~5 days, E2 never reach
412 the 50% of biodegradation ($t_{1/2}$ cannot be estimated). The differences in the results
413 obtained for the different substrate concentration levels could indicate that different
414 mechanisms of biodegradation of trimeprazine enantiomers could exist. On the other
415 hand, as can be observed in all cases, maximum BD values increase with the
416 concentration studied, and as expected according to Figs. 1 and 2, E1 always reach
417 higher BD values than E2 after the enantioselective biodegradation stage.

418

419 *3.4. Precision study under intermediate precision conditions*

420 Precision is often forgotten in biodegradation studies. However, in our opinion,
421 these data should be always provided. For instance, although beyond the aim of this

422 work, the imprecision on S data is probably the most critical variable affecting the
423 quality of kinetic parameters estimation. Also, it could serve to compare different
424 biodegradation procedures. It should be noted that both the analytical method and the
425 biodegradation process, as sources of uncertainty, contribute to the overall precision.

426 The typical design and initial statistics for assessing method precision in such
427 conditions is summarised in section 2.5. The $X_{N_r \times N_s}$ design is consistent with a unique
428 concentration level. However, in the case of biodegradation data, S changes with time
429 due to the degradation process. In these conditions, only the s_r statistic makes sense (Eq.
430 (1)). For each enantiomer, $X_{2 \times 10}$ matrices (2 replicates, 10 days) were built and
431 processed via ANOVA. Considering Eq. (1), the relative standard deviation expressed
432 in percentage (RSD_r) was then calculated according to Eq. (7):

$$RSD_r = \frac{100 \cdot \sqrt{MS_r}}{S_0} \quad (\text{Ec. 7})$$

433 The RSD_r results for each concentration level and enantiomer are shown in
434 Table 1. As can be seen, the RSD_r values range from 3.7 to 8.7%. Those values account
435 the overall method imprecision, including the biodegradation and the analytical
436 processes. This value, habitually unreported, is more relevant than the simply analytical
437 method precision (sometimes reported as part of a validation study).

438 The precision study can be extended to other variables different from
439 concentrations. In this work, a precision study on EF, which accounts for the degree of
440 enantioselective biodegradation, was performed. Considering the fact that the higher
441 noise is concentrate in the last five times (see Fig. 3), and that EF can be considered
442 almost constant in this period, the precision can be performed under intermediate
443 precision conditions (including the factor time; section 2.5).

444 Thus, the last ten EF data (duplicate values), for each concentration level
445 studied, was arranged into $X_{2 \times 5}$ matrices. Considering Eqs. (1) and (2), repeatability and
446 between-run standard deviations can be calculated, as RSD, according to Eqs. (8) and
447 (9):

$$RSD_r = \frac{100 \cdot \sqrt{MS_r}}{EF} \quad (\text{Ec. 8})$$

$$RSD_{run} = 100 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{\frac{MS_{run} - MS_r}{Nr}}}{EF} \quad (\text{Ec. 9})$$

448 Where EF represents the grand mean of X (calculated in section 3.2). As X
449 contain the lowest EF values and imprecise data (the worst case), this procedure
450 provides the maximum EF impression associated with the proposed method. Table 1
451 shows the precision estimates obtained. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first
452 time that a precision study, including between-days EF imprecision estimation, have
453 been reported.

454 Table 1 reveals that $RSD_{run} > RSD_r$. Thus, the use of only RSD_r could provide a
455 false idea of imprecision. On the other hand, the values of $RSD_r (< 5\%)$ and $RSD_{run} (<$
456 $13\%)$ could be considered reasonably normal in the context of a biodegradation process.
457 They suggest that EF estimations can be satisfactorily used to evidence the magnitude
458 of the enantioselectivity of the process.

459

460 **4. Conclusions**

461 Enantiomeric fractions and their standard deviation ($EF \pm s$), at the three
462 concentration levels of trimeprazine studied, offer the first evidence of enantioselective

463 biodegradation of trimeprazine. The maximum enantioselectivity observed (minimum
464 EF value) at three trimeprazine initial racemate concentration (in the 5-20 range) is
465 0.44.

466 The biomass growth (indirectly established by optical density at 600 nm, OD₆₀₀,
467 measurements), suggests that the enantioselective biodegradation process is produced
468 during the stationary/decline stage (more than in the exponential stage). This is an
469 interesting and novel outcome that deserves more attention. We suggest future work
470 with other substrates/biological material to confirm this observation in order to establish
471 if it's a non-isolated fact.

472 The curve fitting method by means of Michaelis-Menten-like approach (solved
473 by the Lambert *W* function approximation), provides S vs. t fitted curves that fit well the
474 S-t experimental data independently of the quality of the parameters. Furthermore, they
475 enable to obtain BD vs. t and, for the first time, EF vs. t fitted curves. From BD vs. t
476 fitted curves, a reasonable estimation of half-life times can be obtained. Such estimation
477 should be more secure than other based on estimated model parameters (e.g. as usual
478 when using first-order kinetics), which can be inaccurate. The similarity between the EF
479 vs. t fitted curves at three concentration curves tested indicates that the
480 enantioselectivity is independent from the concentration. We suggest future work with
481 other substrates/biological material to confirm this observation.

482 The precision study on S (repeatability conditions) and, for the first time, on EF
483 (intermediate precision conditions), suggests that moderate imprecision is observed.
484 Future works focus on estimating the kinetic parameters via Monod (or simplified
485 equations) or also alternative models, should take into account the S imprecision which
486 affects the estimates accuracy. On the other hand, improvements in a biodegradation

487 procedure could be controlled by precision studies by simply comparing the precision
488 outputs.

489 The results obtained in this work correspond to ready biodegradability test
490 obtained in a laboratory scale compatible with the OECD recommendations (whose
491 analyte and microorganisms amounts differ from those in the environment). The
492 moderate enantioselective biodegradation observed for trimeprazine can be considered
493 as indicative of its potential degradation in most environments including biological
494 sewage treatment plants, according to OECD guidelines. On the other hand, a direct
495 extrapolation of the results to the environmental or wastewater treatment scale should
496 not be performed.

497

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502

503 **References**

504 Bagnall, J., Malia, L., Lubben, A., Kasprzyk-Hordem B., 2013. Stereoselective
505 biodegradation of amphetamine and methamphetamine in river microcosms.
506 Water Research 47, 5708-5718.

507 Bagnall, J.P., Evans, S.E., Wort, M.T., Lubben, A.T., Kasprzyk-Hordern, B., 2012.
508 Using chiral liquid chromatography quadrupole time-of-flight mass

509 spectrometry for the analysis of pharmaceuticals and illicit drugs in surface and
510 wastewater at the enantiomeric level. *J. Chromatogr. A* 1249, 115–129.

511 Bonet-Domingo, E., Escuder-Gilabert, L., Medina-Hernández, M.J., Sagrado, S., 2006.
512 Uncertainty-Based Internal Quality Control. Harmonization Considerations.
513 *Anal. Chem.* 78, 8113–8120.

514 Corless, R.M., Gonnet, G.H., Hare, D.E., Jeffrey, D.J., 1993. On the Lambert W
515 function. Technical Report Cs-93-03. Waterloo, Canada: Department of
516 Computer Science, University of Waterloo.

517 Drug Information Portal, 2017. Available at
518 <http://www.druglib.com/activeingredient/trimeprazine/> . Accessed November
519 29, 2017.

520 Ebele, A.J., Abdallah, M. A. E., Harrad, S., 2017. Pharmaceuticals and personal care
521 products (PPCPs) in the freshwater aquatic environment., *Emerging*
522 *Contaminants* 3 ,1-16.

523 Evans, S., Bagnall, J., Kasprzyk-Hordern B., 2017. Enantiomeric profiling of a
524 chemically diverse mixture of chiral pharmaceuticals in urban water.
525 *Environmental Pollution* 230, 368-377.

526 Evans, S.E., Bagnall, J., Kasprzyk-Hordem B., 2016. Enantioselective degradation of
527 amphetamine-like environmental micropollutants (amphetamine,
528 methamphetamine, MDMA and MDA) in urban water. *Environmental*
529 *Pollution* 215, 154-163.

530 Geissen, V., Mol, H., Klumpp, E., Umlauf, G., Nadal, M., van der Ploeg, M., van de
531 Zee, S.E.A.T.M. , Ritsema, C. J., 2015. Emerging pollutants in the

532 environment: A challenge for water resource management. *International Soil*
533 *and Water Conservation Research* 3, 57–65

534 Goudar, C.T., Strevett, K.A. 2000. Estimating in-situ Monod biodegradation parameters
535 using a novel explicit solution of a one-dimensional contaminant transport
536 equation. *Ground Water* 38, 894-898.

537 Her, C., Alonzo, A.P., Vang, J.Y., Torres, E., Krishnan, V.V., 2015. Real-Time Enzyme
538 Kinetics by Quantitative NMR Spectroscopy and Determination of the
539 Michaelis–Menten Constant Using the Lambert-W Function. *J. Chem. Educ.*
540 92, 1943–1948.

541 ISO 9888:1999. Norma UNE-EN ISO 9888. Calidad del agua. Evaluación de la
542 biodegradabilidad aeróbia final de los compuestos orgánicos en medio acuoso.
543 Ensayo estático (Método de Zahn-Wellens). AENOR, Madrid, España, 1999.

544 Kasprzyk-Hordem, B., Baker, D.R., 2012. Enantiomeric Profiling of Chiral Drugs in
545 Wastewater and Receiving Waters. *Environmental Science & Technology* 46
546 (3), 1681-1691.

547 Kasprzyk-Hordern, B., 2010. Pharmacologically active compounds in the environment
548 and their chirality. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 39, 4466-4503

549 Kowalczyk, A., Martin, T.J., Price, O.R, Snape, J.R., van Egmond, R.A., Finnegan,
550 C.J., Schäfer, H., Davenport, R.J., Bending, G.D., 2015. Refinement of
551 biodegradation test methodologies and the proposed utility of new microbial
552 ecology techniques. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 111, 9-22.

553 Kümmerer, K., 2009. The presence of pharmaceuticals in the environment due to human
554 use- present knowledge and future changes. *J. Environ. Manag.* 90, 2354-2366.

- 555 Li, Z., Gomez, E., Fenet, H., Chiron, S., 2013. Chiral signature of venlafaxine as a
556 marker of biological attenuation processes. *Chemosphere* 90 (6), 1933-1938.
- 557 Lin, C.E., Liao, W.S., Cheng, H.T., Kuo, C.M., Liu, Y.C., 2005. Enantioseparation of
558 phenothiazines in cyclodextrin-modified capillary zone electrophoresis using
559 sulfated cyclodextrins as chiral selectors. *Electrophoresis* 26, 3869-3877.
- 560 Liu, C., Zachara, J.M. 2001. Uncertainties of Monod Kinetic parameters nonlinearly
561 estimated from batch experiments. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 35, 133-41
- 562 Maroto, A., Riu, J., Boqué, R., Rius, F. X., 1999. Estimating uncertainties of analytical
563 results using information from the validation process. *Anal. Chim. Acta* 391,
564 173-185.
- 565 Martínez-Gómez, M.A, Sagrado, S., Villanueva-Camañas, R.M., Medina-Hernández
566 M.J., 2007. Enantioseparation of phenothiazines by affinity electrokinetic
567 chromatography using human serum albumin as chiral selector: Application to
568 enantiomeric quality control in pharmaceutical formulations. *Anal. Chim. Acta*
569 582, 223-228.
- 570 Moreira, I.S., Ribeiro, A.R., Afonso, C.M., Castro, Tiritan, M.E., P.M.L., 2014.
571 Enantioselective biodegradation of fluoxetine by the bacterial strain *Labrys*
572 *portucalensis* F11. *Chemosphere* 111, 103-111.
- 573 OECD, 1992. Test No. 302B: Inherent Biodegradability: Zahn-Wellens/EVPA Test,
574 OECD Publishing, Paris. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264070387-en>
- 575 OECD, 2008. Test No. 314: Simulation Tests to Assess the Biodegradability of
576 Chemicals Discharged in Wastewater, OECD Publishing, Paris. DOI:
577 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264067493-en>.

578 Oguni, K., Oda, H., Ichida, A. 1995. Development of chiral stationary phases consisting
579 of polysaccharide derivatives. *J. Chromatogr. A* 694, 91-100.

580 Petrie, B., Barden, R., Kasprzyk-Hordern, B., 2015. A review on emerging
581 contaminants in wastewaters and the environment: Current knowledge,
582 understudied areas and recommendations for future monitoring. *Water*
583 *Research* 72, 3-27

584 Ribeiro, A.R., Afonso, C.M., Castro, P.M.L., Tiritan, M.E, 2013a. Enantioselective
585 HPLC analysis and biodegradation of atenolol, metoprolol and fluoxetine.
586 *Environ. Chem. Lett.* 11 (1), 83-90.

587 Ribeiro, A.R., Afonso, C.M., Castro, P.M.L., Tiritan, M.E., 2013b. Enantioselective
588 biodegradation of pharmaceuticals, alprenolol and propranolol, by an activated
589 sludge inoculum. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 87, 108-114.

590 Ribeiro, A.R., Castro, P.M.L., Tiritan, M.E. 2012. Environmental Fate of Chiral
591 Pharmaceuticals: Determination, Degradation and Toxicity. In: Lichtfouse E.,
592 Schwarzbauer J., Robert D. (eds) *Environmental Chemistry for a Sustainable*
593 *World*. Springer, Dordrecht.

594 Ribeiro, A.R., Maia, A.S., Moreira, I.S., Afonso, C.M., Castro, P.M.L., Tiritan, M.E.,
595 2014b. Enantioselective quantification of fluoxetine and norfluoxetine by
596 HPLC in wastewater effluents. *Chemosphere* 95, 589-596.

597 Ribeiro, A.R., Santos, L.H.M.L.M., Maia, A.S., Delerue-Matos, C., Castro, P.M.L.,
598 Tiritan, M.E., 2014a. Enantiomeric fraction evaluation of pharmaceuticals in
599 environmental matrices by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry.
600 *J. Chromatogr. A* 1363, 226-235.

601 Robinson, J.A., Tiedje, J.M. 1983. Nonlinear estimation of Monod Growth kinetic
602 parameters from a single substrate depletion curve. Appl. Environ.
603 Microbiol.45, 1453-1458.

604 Royal Society of Chemistry, 2017. Available at
605 [http://www.rsc.org/Membership/Networking/InterestGroups/Analytical/AMC/
606 Software/RobustStatistics.asp](http://www.rsc.org/Membership/Networking/InterestGroups/Analytical/AMC/Software/RobustStatistics.asp). Accessed November 9, 2017.

607 Sánchez, F. G., Navas Díaz, A., Sánchez Torreño, E., Aguilar, A., Medina Lama I.,
608 Algarra M., 2012. Determination of enantiomeric excess by chiral liquid
609 chromatography without enantiomerically pure starting standards. Biomed.
610 Chromatogr. 26, 1241-1246.

611 Sanganyado, E., Lu, Z., Fu, Q., Schlenk, D., Gan, J., 2017. Chiral pharmaceuticals: A
612 review on their environmental occurrence and fate processes. Water Research
613 124, 527-542.

614 Shuler, M.L., Kargi, F. (Eds.), 2002. Bioprocess Engineering: Basic Concepts, 2nd ed.,
615 Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ.

616 Stanley, J.K., Ramirez, A.J., Chambliss, Brooks, B.W., 2007. Enantiospecific sublethal
617 effects of the antidepressant fluoxetine to a model aquatic vertebrate and
618 invertebrate, Chemosphere 69, 9-16.

619 Stanley, J.K., Ramirez, A.J., Mottaleb, M., Chambliss, C.K., Brooks, B.W., 2006.
620 Enantiospecific toxicity of the β -blocker propranolol to *Daphnia magna* and
621 *Pimephales promelas*. Environ Toxicol. Chem. 25, 1780-1786.

622 Thouand, G., 2014. Biodegradability assessments of organic substances and polymers.
623 Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res. 21, 9443-9444.

624 Van Overbeke, A.A.L., Baeyens, W.R.G., Beyaert, A., Aboul-Enein, H.Y., Oda, H.,
625 1997. Chiral Resolution of Several Phenothiazine Compounds and
626 Trimipramine, a Dibenzazepine Drug on Chiralcel OJ-R. *J. Liq. Chrom. & Rel.*
627 *Technol.* 20, 693-705.

628 Vazquez-Roig, P., Kasprzyk-Hordem, B., Blasco, C., Picó Y., 2014. Stereoisomeric
629 profiling of drugs of abuse and pharmaceuticals in wastewaters of Valencia
630 (Spain). *Sci. Total Environ.* 494-495, 49-57.

631 Wong, C.S., 2006. Environmental fate processes and biochemical transformations of
632 chiral emerging organic pollutants. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 386, 544–558.

633

634

635 **Figure captions**

636 **Figure 1.** Chromatograms corresponding to a sample solution containing 9 mg.L^{-1} of
637 trimeprazine, after 0 (curve 1) and 18 days of incubation (curve 2). E1 and E2 refer to
638 the first and second eluting enantiomer.

639

640 **Figure 2.** Concentration versus time experimental data (two replicates) of trimeprazine
641 enantiomers. First (Δ) and second (∇) eluted enantiomers. Fitted curves (solid lines)
642 from the simplified Monod model (Eq. (5)). Optical density at 600 nm (OD, \bullet , dashed
643 line). Initial trimeprazine racemate concentration: 9 mg.L^{-1} .

644

645 **Figure 3.** Mean enantiomeric fraction and standard deviation ($\text{EF} \pm s$, points with error
646 bars). EF vs. time fitted curve (solid line) consistent with the simplified Monod models.
647 The horizontal line at $\text{EF} = 0.5$ represents no enantioselective biodegradation.

648

649 **Figure 4.** Biodegradation (BD) in percentage of trimeprazine enantiomers estimated
650 from the simplified Monod models. Initial racemate concentrations: 4.8 mg.L^{-1} for
651 curves 1 (E1) and 2 (E2); 9 mg.L^{-1} for curves 3 (E1) and 4 (E2); 18 mg.L^{-1} for curves 5
652 (E1) and 6 (E2). The dashed line at $\text{BD} = 50\%$ is included. E1 and E2 refer to the first
653 and second eluted enantiomer.

654

Table 1[Click here to download Table: Table1R1.docx](#)

Table 1. Method statistics

Method Calibration				
Enantiomer	Interval ^a , mg.L ⁻¹	Regression curve equation	R ²	
E1	1-30	$y = - 3.65 + 8.29 x$	0.994	
E2		$y = - 4.04 + 8.83 x$	0.994	
Method precision		Concentration ^b	Enantiomeric fraction (EF) ^c	
Enantiomer	Level ^a , mg.L ⁻¹	RSD _r %	RSD _r %	RSD _{run} %
E1	4.8	6.7	4.9	7.3
E2		6.2		
E1	9	4.2	3.5	9.8
E2		8.7		
E1	18	5.9	3.6	12.4
E2		3.7		

E1 and E2 refer to the first and second eluted enantiomers, respectively. R² is the coefficient of determination. RSD_r is the relative standard deviation in repeatability conditions. RSD_{run} is the relative standard deviation in intermediate precision conditions (including the factor time).

^a Racemate concentration.

^b Concentration data for the whole time period evaluated; eq. 7.

^c EF data for the last five days; eqs. 8 and 9.

Figure1

Fig. 1.

Figure2

Fig. 2

Figure3

Fig. 3

Figure4

Fig. 4